

DIALOGUE OF CULTURES AS AN ORGANIC PRINCIPLE FOR FORMING
TOLERANCE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

International conflicts as challenges of the time actualize the problem of finding peaceful coexistence and international harmony. The importance of developing tolerance from childhood requires modern methods of pedagogical influence that have deep methodological and cultural-historical foundations. These include the principle of dialogue of cultures, which promotes the development of tolerant feelings and views based on the dialogical interaction of individuals, different mentalities, and works of art.

Key words: tolerance, diversity, preschoolers, dialogue of cultures, relationships, assessments, cultural meanings.

The problem of developing tolerance is currently becoming particularly acute due to the aggravation of international conflicts, the intensification of the phenomena of terrorism and extremism, and the involvement of young people in various destructive groups and organizations.

From the first days of its independence, Uzbekistan has been paying special attention to strengthening interethnic harmony and cooperation [1,2,4,5]. A political and legal framework has been created, equality and constitutional rights of all citizens of Uzbekistan have been ensured, regardless of their nationality and religion. Since ancient times, in Uzbekistan, traditions of benevolence, hospitality, compassion, empathy, mutual assistance, honor and respect have existed, strengthened and existed. The understanding of cultural, religious and linguistic diversity as a natural property of a modern progressive state has become firmly established in the public consciousness. All this testifies to the generally successful implementation of the principles of tolerance in society.

The task of the current stage is to actively implement the process of forming a tolerant attitude of the younger generation from an early age in order to prevent the penetration of inhumane ideas of hostility, aggressiveness, propaganda of rejection and violence into the minds of children and youth.

In preschool age, initial moral values and norms of behavior are laid, ideas about the importance of human dignity are formed, an understanding of the value of one's own personality and other people is developed, respect for them, a sense of solidarity and a desire for cooperation, and the ability to non-violently resolve conflicts are developed.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a multinational state, therefore it is necessary to comprehensively introduce children not only to the culture of their people, but also to respectful, kind attitude towards representatives of other cultures and nationalities from preschool age. Ethnic and socio-economic differences that exist between children growing up in different environments should be taken into account.

Scientists and teachers in many countries believe that cultivating a respectful attitude towards other people and showing interest in them is necessary from preschool age, when the child is "open" to the influence of cultures.

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Considering the strengthening of negative trends taking place in the world, the echoes of which reach Uzbekistan, it is necessary to look for new methods and forms of teaching tolerance to preschoolers, which include the principle of dialogue of cultures.

The dialogue of cultures as a process of interaction between participants in the educational process, the formation and manifestation of tolerance fills it with cultural meanings.

Preschool education workers must convey to the new generation the ethical rules of attitude towards other cultures and their representatives: treat representatives of different nationalities with respect and respect, understand that people are equal in their dignity and rights, although they differ in nationality. Be aware of the peculiarities of the lifestyle, psychology, traditions, culture, social and ethical priorities of other people. It is in childhood that mental functions actively develop, the development of more complex types and techniques of mental, physical, communicative, and creative activity begins, which subsequently play a vital role in the socialization and self-determination of the child's personality. The foundations of tolerance are laid in preschoolers during work in the classroom, during leisure time, in independent play and aesthetic and creative activities, when visiting children's libraries, performances, and museums.

Author E.A. Zhestkova believes that the dialogue of cultures is considered as a pedagogical concept, from which unique approaches to education and all kinds of methods flow. In her opinion, in modern pedagogy, the dialogue of cultures is a principle and an effective tool for training and educating the younger generation, with the help of which education is carried out [7].

This statement appears to us as vague and non-specific, while a number of scientists (S.A. Abdullaeva, L.M. Rizaeva, O.A. Harutyunyan, T.G. Melnik, L.V. Ershova, N.M. Ivanova, T.A. Chernova, Zh.V. Marchenko, etc.) unanimously emphasize the role of dialogue as an integral property of tolerance in relationships, assessments, views, and actions [3,6,8,9,10,11,2,13].

The concept of tolerance always implies the presence of two (dialogue) or several (polylogue) subjects. Tolerance (tolerance, understanding, acceptance, interaction) is the quality of an individual or a group of people; dialogue in its pure form, as a general concept - communication between two people or a group of people; dialogue of cultures is a principle that exists at the intersection of philosophy, cultural studies, psychology and is expressed in communication, the exchange of values at the level of cultural meanings (internal dialogue - a person with himself, between a work of art and a person, between a teacher and a student as representatives of a certain culture). From the above it follows that the formation of tolerance based on the principle of dialogue of cultures is an organic process.

It is legitimate to assume that in order to achieve an effective result from the application of this principle, the teacher (educator) needs to understand its essence and successfully apply it in practical work with children, teach children to communicate calmly and kindly with each other.

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